

STUDIES ON THE REACTION BETWEEN CUPRIC AND THIOSULPHATE IONS IN SOLUTION

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The reaction between Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ in solution has been studied by thermometric and conductometric titrations and absorption measurements. Reactions are indicated when Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions are present in solution in the molar ratios of 1:6, 1:3, 4:9 and 2:3 respectively, indicating the formation of various complex cuprothiosulphates in solution.

It has been found that bivalent copper is completely reduced to the monovalent state when 9 moles of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ have been added to 4 moles of Cu^{2+} and a probable mechanism underlying the reduction has been suggested.

A large number of thiosulphate complexes of monovalent copper has been described in the literature. Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1913, 11, 650) isolated a product of the composition $4\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and obtained evidence of the formation of the compounds $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 9\text{M}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{M}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{M}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ from conductivity and E.M.F. titrations of copper salts solutions with alkali thiosulphates. Basset and Durrant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 128, 1279) obtained three complex cuprothiosulphates viz., $3\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{N}_1\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and $2\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$, on mixing solutions of copper salts and sodium thiosulphate at different concentrations, although in each case the proportion of copper salt and thiosulphate was 1:2 molar in the mixture. Spacu and Murgulescu (*Bull. Soc. Stinte. Cluj*, 1930, 5, 61, 254), employing potentiometric titrations of solutions of copper salts with solutions of thiosulphates of Na, K and NH_4 , concluded that the following complex ions might exist in solutions, e.g., $[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)]^-$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]^{2-}$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]^{3-}$ and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]^{4-}$.

Ryabchikov and Nichenko (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U.R.S.S. Classe Sci. Chem.*, 1947, 19-26), however, considered that most of the solid compounds previously described in the literature were impure. According to these authors, depending on the ratio of Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ in solution, only three types of products are formed, viz. $\text{Na}[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)]$, $\text{Na}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$ and $\text{Na}_4[\text{Cu}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]$.

The compounds $\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{Na}[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$ and $\text{Cu}^+\text{Na}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$, obtained by these authors, are regarded as products of interaction of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$ with excess of Cu^{2+} and Cu^+ ions respectively.

It thus appears that although a large number of complex cuprothiosulphates has been prepared in the solid state, in solution the reaction between Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions has not been studied systematically, and where this has been made, contradictory results have often been obtained. Also, the mechanism of the reduction of bivalent copper to the monovalent state by thiosulphate is not quite clear. An attempt has

therefore been made by the author to secure information in these respects by employing thermometric and conductometric titrations and absorption measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper sulphate, copper nitrate and sodium thiosulphate, employed for the preparation of stock solutions, were of E. Merck's A.R. quality, recrystallised from distilled water. The stock solutions, which were of molar order, were all made in air-free distilled water, which was used for all subsequent dilutions to required strengths.

Thermometric Titrations

The thermometric apparatus and the method of titration were the same as that of Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1922, 19, 324). Titrations, both direct and reverse, were performed. The enthalpy change curves (Figs. 1 and 2) obtained with different concentrations of the reactants were drawn by plotting the heat changes at constant volume ΔT_{c_v} against the volume of the titrant. (Here

$$\Delta T_{c_v} = \frac{\Delta T(V+v)}{V},$$

where ΔT = the observed change in temp. in °C, arising from the addition of v c.c. of the titrant to V c.c. of the solution taken in the Dewar vessel). This method of plotting is due to the author (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 366; 1957, 34, 407; 1958, 35, 57) and adequately compensates for any error due to the effect of dilution in the graphical representation of the temperature change process. The thermometric curves show breaks when Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions are present in the molar ratios of 1:6, 1:3, 4:9 and 2:3 (of which the breaks at 1:6 and 4:9 are common in both direct and reverse titrations), indicating interaction of these ions in such proportions.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Conductivity Measurements

The conductivity apparatus consisted of a box-type conductivity bridge of Leeds and Northrup Co., Philadelphia, U.S.A. An audiofrequency oscillator was used as a current source and a visual indicator served to indicate the null point. The conductivity cell was kept in a thermostat maintained at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. Only direct conductometric titrations of solutions of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ by copper salt solutions were performed—the reverse titrations could not be carried out as the products formed in solution underwent slow decomposition in absence of excess of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$. Fig. 3 represents the conductance-composition curves. The curves are characterised by breaks indicating interactions between Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ in the ratios of 1:6 and 4:9. No break appears in the ratio 1:3 or 2:3, which is seen in the thermometric curves (Fig. 1). Moreover, the break at the ratio 1:6 disappears at large dilutions (Fig. 3, curve C).

Absorption Measurements

Since the colour of copper salt in solution changed from blue to yellow and finally became colorless upon gradual addition of sodium thiosulphate solution, absorption measurements of mixtures of copper salts (sulphate and nitrate) in solution with sodium thiosulphate solution was resorted to in order to elucidate the mechanism underlying the reduction of cupric ion by thiosulphate, and this has been done by using the Lumetron photoelectric colorimeter (Model 402E) of the Photovolt Corporation, U.S.A., a constant voltage transformer (120V.A) being used to stabilise the light source.

FIG. 3

CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION CURVES OF
 $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ WITH CuSO_4 & $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$

The course of the reduction of Cu^{2+} to Cu^+ was followed by working at 700 $\text{m}\mu$, where the Cu^{2+} ion had a strong absorption, that of the yellow-coloured body being nil. %Transmissions of the mixtures of copper salt and sodium thiosulphate solutions were found to change slightly at first, then remain constant for sometime and finally fall off rapidly as the solution became turbid in course of a few minutes. Hence, direct measurements of the transmission values, setting the balance cell off, were carried out at intervals of 10 seconds, starting from the instant of mixing, the values of % transmission at equilibrium being employed for plotting.

The differences in the optical densities of the mixtures Δ (O.D.) from those of the copper salt solutions alone have been plotted graphically against the compositions of

the mixtures in Fig. 4. It will be noted that the maxima in the Δ (O.D.)—composition curves occur at the molar ratio of $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 4:9$ at all concentrations of the reacting ions. Also the absorption due to the Cu^{2+} ions altogether vanishes whenever such ions are present in the above ratio. This evidently indicates that divalent copper is quantitatively reduced to monovalent state when 4 moles of a thio-sulphate are added to 1 mole of a cupric salt in solution.

FIG. 4

DISCUSSION

From the method of investigations employed so far, it is clear that in solutions, depending on the concentrations of reactants, reaction occurs mainly in four different proportions, viz. 1:6, 1:3, 4:9 and 2:3 moles of Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions respectively.

If the primary reaction, which is an oxidation-reduction process, is represented as

the reactions in the proportions $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 1:6$ and $1:3$ may be explained as occurring in the following stages :

(I). $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 1:6$:

(II). $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 1 : 3 :$

Adding, $2 \text{Cu}^{2+} + 6 \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 2[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]^{2-} + \text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-} \dots (3)$

The formation of the compounds $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 9\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ or $\text{Na}_9[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]$ and $\text{Na}_3[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$, described by Dutoit (*loc. cit.*) and Ryabchikov (*loc. cit.*), are thus accounted for.

The break in the thermometric curves, at $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 1 : 3$, apparently indicates the completion of the primary reaction (1). But this cannot be true firstly because $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ is too unstable to exist in the free state; secondly when solutions of copper salt and thiosulphate are mixed in this proportion, the mixture takes a green colour, indicating the presence of unreduced Cu^{2+} ion in considerable amounts. On the other hand, the break at 2 : 3 can be assigned to the formation of the compound $\text{Cu}^{2+}\text{Na}[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$, described by the Russian workers (*loc. cit.*), in the following way :

(III). $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 2 : 3 :$

From equation (3)

Adding, $4 \text{CuX}_2 + 6 \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 = 2 \text{Cu}^{2+}\text{Na}[\text{Cu}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2] + \text{Na}_2\text{S}_4\text{O}_6 + 8 \text{NaX} \dots (5)$

The simplest interpretation of the reaction indicated in the ratio of $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 4 : 9$ is to assume that a complex product $\text{Na}_6[\text{Cu}_4(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]$ is formed as follows :

The structure of $[\text{Cu}_4(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3]^{-6}$ ion is, however, not clear. But we cannot totally discount the possibility of the existence of this species in solution as an ammonium compound of analogous formula $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ has been prepared by Dasset and Durrant (*loc. cit.*). The yellow compound $3\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, isolated by the same workers, which is usually written as $\text{Na}_4[\text{Cu}_6(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (cf. Partington, "General and Inorganic Chemistry", p. 722) requires that the reaction between Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ should occur when these ions are in the molar ratio of 6 : 11, as shown by the following equation :

No evidence of such a reaction is provided by the present methods of study and the solid product of the above composition, in all probability, is a mixture of two or more substances. It also appears highly probable from the variety of solid products formed, when Cu^{2+} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ ions are present in solution in proportions around the ratio of 1 : 2 moles, that reaction at this proportion results in the formation of several complexes instead of one, as previously supposed. On this assumption, the interaction of Cu^{2+}

and $S_2O_3^{2-}$ in the ratio of 4 : 9, indicated by thermometric, conductometric and absorption studies, may be well explained by the following overall reaction giving rise to three different complex products of simple compositions :

The compounds $Cu^+Na_2[(Cu(S_2O_3)_2)]$ and $Na[Cu(S_2O_3)]$, described by Ryabchikov and Nichenko (*loc.cit.*) are presumably formed by the following exchange reaction :

The reaction envisaged in equation (7) also explains why complete reduction of Cu^{2+} by $S_2O_3^{2-}$ occurs when these ions are present in the molar ratio of 4 : 9.

The second explanation appears all the more plausible considering that we have no other direct evidence regarding the formation of the compounds $Cu^+Na_2[Cu(S_2O_3)_2]$ and $Na[Cu(S_2O_3)]$ isolated by the previous workers.

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